

Design of Nanomaterials in Hydrogen Storage

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Abstract

Nowadays hydrogen is considered to be a very useful fuel as it produces huge amount of energy along with water as the only by product after burning with oxygen. But it is very difficult to store for a long time, as it is having the least molecular size and is capable of escaping even from intermolecular space of all materials, including metals. Researchers are engaged to find a probable solution; they are trying to find the ways to bind hydrogen molecules in a material matrix. The molecular interaction of hydrogen molecules with that of the other solids materials and the mechanisms of hydride formation by chemical bond formation, lead to many significant changes in nanomaterials' microstructures, hence the properties. The objectives of this review work are to describe the design principles of materials, to verify the properties changes and their suitability in hydrogen storage applications. Here we have discussed the effects of microstructure of the nanomaterials' on their hydrogen sorption efficiency. Several nanocomposites are developed e.g., bulk-heterojunction nanomaterials synthesised by physico-mechanical as well as chemical routes, multilayers coatings, single layer thin films and, nanocomposite structures such as core-shell structure or composite nanoparticles, and nanoparticles on porous structure e.g., graphene base materials, etc. There are reports that some bimetallic and trimetallic materials are very suitable for the hydrogen storage applications. Nanostructured materials e.g., carbon nanotubes, boron nitride, magnesium based nanohydrides, carbon based nanocomposites, polymer based nanocomposites, and metal organic frameworks structure (MOFs) are considered to be prospective candidates for storing large quantities of hydrogen gas. In addition, other carbon based nanomaterials e.g. fullerenes, nanofibers, polyaniline nanospheres and their hydrogen storage properties are discussed.

Key words: Hydrogen storage, Nanomaterials, Hydrides, Metal Organic Frameworks, Sorption properties

1. Introduction:

Hydrogen is traditionally used in many industries for different purposes e.g., (i) to make ammonia in fertilizer industry, (ii) to remove sulphur from fuels in oil-refining processes, (iii) to manufacture silicon chips in semiconductor industry, and (iv) to hydrogenate oils in the food industry [1, 2]. It is also a common reactant or a byproduct in the specialty chemical and pharmaceutical industries.

Hydrogen has its inherent risk, as it is lighter than air; it dissipates rapidly when it is released, unlike hydrocarbon-based fuels. It claims unique safety challenge, so it is important to every industry to know and understand how to identify and mitigate hazards associated with hydrogen. Hydrogen storage and its transportation require a key technology that may be suitable for power generation. Hydrogen has the highest specific energy (i.e., energy/mass) at low temperature compared to all other fuels [3]. But it has low energy density at room temperature i.e., it has a low energy per unit volume. It requires an advanced storage method for its safe handling and operation. Hydrogen can be stored in the form of either a gaseous state or a liquid state. Storage of hydrogen in the form gaseous state requires typically high-pressure

in the range of 350–700 bar [4]. Whereas, the storage of hydrogen in the form of liquid state requires very low temperature as the boiling point of hydrogen at 1 atm. pressure is about -252.8°C . Hydrogen can also be captured either on the surface of the solids by the adsorption mechanism or within

solids by the absorption mechanism. There was a first report that the hydrogen gas may be stored in hollow glass microspheres [5].

2. Hydrogen Storage Mechanism

Hydrogen is stored in different forms e.g., (i) compressed hydrogen, (ii) liquefied hydrogen, (iii) chemical storage, and (iv) metal organic frameworks.

(i) Compressed hydrogen

Hydrogen can be stored under compression to increase its density (Fig.1). The compressed hydrogen is stored in a tank of vehicle, the tank materials are based on carbon based nanocomposites [6]. The different manufacturers of cars e.g., Honda or Nissan, are also using this technology. Another class of materials are Zeolites; they are microporous and highly crystalline silicate materials with a major component of alumina. They exhibit cage and tunnel structures, so they offer good properties for the encapsulation of non-polar gases including H_2 . Here the hydrogen interacts physically on the surface of the zeolite pores by the adsorption mechanism that requires hydrogen to be forced into the pores under pressure and low temperature. It is found that the gas storage capacity depends mainly on the BET surface area, pore volume of the microstructure, interaction of hydrogen with internal surfaces of the micropores, and working conditions such as temperature and pressure.

Fig.1 Compressed Gas Manufacturing Plant

(ii) Liquefied hydrogen

Hydrogen may be liquefied by decreasing its temperature to -253°C , as we do for liquefaction of natural gas (LNG) (Fig 2). The storage tank developed for the liquid hydrogen is nowadays used in modern cars, e.g., BMW Hydrogen 7. To increase the performance of storage tank, activated carbons may be used, as they have highly permeable structures and amorphous in nature, thereby having high surface area per unit mass. It was reported that the hydrogen adsorption capacity of these materials was increased with increasing the surface area; however, this increment is not continuous, an optimizing pore diameter was achieved [7].

Fig.2 Liquid Hydrogen Manufacturing Plant

(iii) Chemical storage

Here, the chemical storage refers that the hydrogen is covalently bonded with other materials in either of their solid state or liquid state. These types of the compounds offer the highest efficiency of hydrogen storage. Afterwards, the hydrogen is released from the chemically bonded hydrogen systems in either by the exothermic or endothermic processes. The hydrogen is regenerated by rehydrogenation typically by pressure release or by heating. This approach is suitable for a single-use and high-value-added compounds. It is applicable in large hydrogen storage and transportation systems. However, the mechanism of formation of the complex hydrogen compounds and afterwards its release from that complex structure, are very complicated mechanism, so cannot be easily predicted.

The dehydrogenation of the chemically bonded hydrogen is possible by two methods, e.g., hydrolytical method or thermolytical method, the later one needs heating of the compound. For study in details of these two mechanisms, ammonia borane (NH_3BH_3) and alane (AlH_3) were considered. The high hydrogen storage capacity of ammonia borane compound, amide or amine compounds, is drawing interest nowadays. In the case of hydrides complex formation, the reaction mechanism for dehydrogenation of chemically bonded hydrogen is a very complex in nature; however, if the product remains in the form of liquid phase or slurry phase, then it can be handled easily. In addition to covalently bonded hydrogen in solids, there are many compounds that can bind hydrogen in the liquid forms, e.g., n-ethylcarbazole and methylcyclopentane etc.

Silicon has an excellent hydrogen-storage capacity; hydrogen is captured on the porous structure of silicon. The large volume expansion occurs during the hydrogen storage in the silicon matrix whereas, the volume contraction occurs when there is a release of that hydrogen gas. So there is a chance of seriously damaging the structural stability of silicon matrix during the storing and releasing cycles. In order to increase the pore volumes in silicon nanostructures and to improve the cyclic stability of the microstructure, different types of silicon allotropes are generally used. The results showed that the spaces around these microstructures are useful to provide a larger degree of empty spaces. The low structural dimension of silicon allotropes shows a high chemical hydrogen storage capacity. Moreover, hydrogen gas molecules may diffuse into the surface of silicon microstructure as well as between two closely bonded silicon microstructures. Graphene has double bonds in its backbone microstructure, so it can store gaseous hydrogen by the chemical bond formation. Once the H_2 added to these double bonds, the graphene giving rise graphane compound; in next course of action, this hydrogen is released on heating at around of 450°C .

(iv) Metal-organic frameworks (MOFs)

Metal-organic frameworks (MOFs) are highly crystalline materials in inorganic as well as organic in nature. The hybrid structures of MOFs that contain metal clusters or ions as the secondary building units, and organic ligands as linkers. If the guest molecules e.g., hydrogen or solvents are removed on heating under vacuum, the porous structures of MOFs are formed without interfering the original structures of MOFs. The hydrogen gases are adsorbed on the surfaces of the pore structure of the materials by the adsorption process. These types of MOFs are found in zeolites and amorphous carbon materials. These materials have a high number of pores and their surface structure has a high affinity to higher hydrogen uptake for a constant volume of the matrix. There are several research works on hydrogen storage capacity of MOFs [8]. Since there are indefinite number of geometries and chemical compositions of MOFs for different proportions of the materials; it is important to know at what combination the hydrogen uptake will be the maximum. It has been found that the temperature, pressure and composition of the matrix can change the hydrogen storage capacity of MOFs. The adsorption capacity of hydrogen on the MOFs surface is lower at high temperature and is higher at low temperature. This may be due to increase and decrease of kinetic energy of with increasing or decreasing temperature, respectively. With the increasing temperature, the rate of the gas adsorption process decreases and however, the chemisorption process increases. So the total adsorption capacity may not be predicted with the process condition. For instance, some compounds have the highest total gas adsorption capacity, but show a very less extent of effective volume of the bonded hydrogen. Absorption capacity of the matrix can be increased by modification of surface structure. For example, the hydrogen adsorption of PCN-68 composites is higher than that of PCN-61 [9]. The PAF-1 is reported to have a porous aromatic structure with a high surface area; its surface area may be increased by doping with some metals.

(i) Adsorbent
(e.g., Metal Oxide,
Framework)

(ii) Liquid Organic
(e.g., BN-Methyl,
cyclopentane)

(iii) Interstitial Hydride
(e.g., LaNi_5H_6),

(iv) Complex Hydride, (v) Chemical Hydrogen
(e.g., NaAlH₄) (e.g., NH₃BH₃)

Fig.3 Different Hydrogen Storage Precursors

3. Future prospect of Hydrogen storage

As we know hydrogen is having light weight, and is storable with an energy-dense arrangement, and produces no direct emission of pollutant materials. But if hydrogen is used as a clean energy, it needs some utmost care in production, storage, transportation, and uses. In future the more uses of hydrogen will help us in providing an extensive and independent energy solution which can help to achieve a clean and affordable energy source. The supply of hydrogen gases to different industries is now a lucrative business around the world. The requirement of hydrogen is continuously increasing and it is found that there is about threefold increase since 1975.

In the materials e.g., zeolites, clathrates, MOFs, porous carbons, and polymers, the hydrogen is absorbed by physical mechanism on the surface of the material matrix (Fig.3). The hydrogen storage capacity primarily depends on the surface area and porosity of the materials. The major

limitation to use of these materials as the sorbents of H₂ materials is its poor van der Waals forces between hydrogen and the surface of the materials. The many of these materials have high capacities of storing at high pressures and low temperature, but this capacity become very low at room temperature and at normal atmospheric pressure.

The current technologies are still far from being commercially use [10, 11]. Many research studies are going on but the most of cases it is done in the laboratory scale. So the actual hazards associated with the large materials handling and for scale up scenario, the actual technology will be a different. It may require a very high pressure and low temperatures as a principle. So at present these technology are not considered as a novel technology. However, in near future, we will have a valuable and efficient solution for the compression and liquefaction processes of hydrogen and we can solve our future energy needs.

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